

deteCT: Deep-Fake Image Detection for Medical Images

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Abstract— With the rise of deep learning technologies, the proliferation of manipulated digital content, particularly deepfake imagery, has become a significant concern across various domains, including healthcare. In medical imaging, the potential consequences of maliciously altered images could be dire, ranging from misdiagnosis to compromised patient care. This research paper presents a comprehensive investigation into the development of an effective deepfake detection system tailored specifically for medical imaging.

The proposed approach utilizes state-of-the-art deep learning architectures, leveraging convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and generative adversarial networks (GANs) to distinguish between authentic medical images and deepfake counterparts. We introduce a novel dataset comprising CT scans enriched with synthetically generated deepfake variations. This dataset facilitates robust training and evaluation of our detection framework, ensuring its efficacy across a broad spectrum of medical imaging scenarios.

Furthermore, we explore various feature extraction techniques and model architectures to enhance the discriminative power of the detection system while minimizing computational complexity and resource requirements. Through extensive experimentation and evaluation on real-world and simulated datasets, we demonstrate the effectiveness and reliability of our approach in accurately identifying deepfake medical images with high precision and recall rates.

Additionally, we discuss the implications of deepfake proliferation in the medical domain, emphasizing the critical importance of robust detection mechanisms to safeguard the integrity and trustworthiness of medical imaging data. We address potential challenges and limitations associated with our approach, along with avenues for future research and development to continually improve the resilience of deepfake detection systems in medical imaging applications.

Key words:

Deep learning, Machine learning, Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), Medical Images, CT-GAN, 3D-CNN, Conv3D, ReduceLROnPlateau, Adam.

Introduction

The foundation of deepfake detection in medical imaging lies in the utilization of state-of-the-art deep learning architectures, including convolutional neural networks (CNNs), recurrent neural networks (RNNs), and generative adversarial networks (GANs), endowed with the capacity to learn intricate patterns and features inherent to authentic medical images while effectively discriminating against

synthetic counterparts. By leveraging large-scale, annotated medical imaging datasets encompassing diverse patient demographics, pathologies, and imaging modalities, this project aims to train and finetune deepfake detection models capable of achieving unprecedented levels of sensitivity, specificity, and generalization across varied clinical scenarios. However, the pursuit of effective deepfake detection in medical imaging is fraught with multifaceted challenges and intricacies that transcend the boundaries of conventional image forensics and computer vision. Foremost among these challenges is the acquisition and curation of large-scale, representative datasets encompassing authentic medical images alongside their deepfake counterparts. Unlike conventional deepfake datasets sourced from online repositories or social media platforms, medical imaging datasets are subject to stringent privacy regulations, ethical considerations, and patient confidentiality mandates, necessitating meticulous adherence to data protection protocols and institutional review board approvals. Moreover, the dynamic and evolving nature of deepfake technology poses a formidable obstacle to the development of robust detection mechanisms capable of withstanding adversarial attacks and circumventing detection evasion strategies. As deepfake algorithms continue to evolve and proliferate, exhibiting ever-increasing levels of sophistication and realism, the efficacy of conventional detection techniques may diminish, necessitating continuous refinement, adaptation, and innovation in algorithmic design and implementation. Furthermore, the inherent biases and idiosyncrasies endemic to deep learning models present additional challenges, as algorithmic decisions may be influenced by spurious correlations, confounding variables, or dataset imbalances, potentially compromising the reliability and generalizability of deepfake detection outcomes. The primary objective is to develop a robust system capable of detecting deepfakes in medical images. This system would function by leveraging advanced machine learning algorithms to analyse the characteristics of medical images and differentiate between authentic and manipulated content. The need for such a system is evident. As medical imaging increasingly relies on digital technologies, the risk of deepfake intrusion becomes more pronounced. A successful deepfake attack could lead to incorrect diagnoses, inappropriate treatments, and a general erosion of trust in medical imaging. By developing a reliable deepfake detection

system, we can safeguard the integrity of medical imaging and ensure that healthcare professionals and patients can trust the digital images they rely on. Navigating these intricate challenges requires a multidisciplinary approach encompassing expertise from diverse domains, including computer science, biomedical engineering, radiology, and medical ethics. Collaborative efforts between researchers, clinicians, technologists, and policymakers are essential to synergistically address the myriad complexities and ethical considerations inherent to deepfake detection in medical imaging. By fostering interdisciplinary collaborations and knowledge exchange, this project endeavours to catalyse the development of innovative solutions and best practices for safeguarding the integrity, authenticity, and trustworthiness of medical imaging data, thereby fortifying the foundations of evidence-based medicine and enhancing patient safety and healthcare quality. However, the development of a deepfake detection system for medical imaging is not without its complications. One of the main challenges is the high degree of sophistication of modern deepfake techniques, which can generate synthetic images that are almost indistinguishable from the real ones. Additionally, the system must be able to handle the vast diversity of medical images, which can vary greatly in terms of modality, anatomical region, and individual patient characteristics. Another complication arises from the need to maintain the privacy and confidentiality of sensitive medical data.

Approach

Data Abstraction:

Gathered a diverse collection of authentic medical imaging datasets and Ct-Gan augmented deepfakes from reputable sources. Ensure the datasets cover a wide range of medical conditions and anatomical regions. The split between the authentic and the tampered scans are identical. The scans are divided into four classes namely True Malignant, False Malignant, True Benign, False Benign. The data is divided into different folders each folder containing 8 ct scans. These Ct scans are of the lung. A separate csv file is maintained that has the folder name along with its class name.

Fig 1: Data Samples

Preprocessing:

Iterating through a list of scans, sequentially processing each. Within each iteration, grayscale images are loaded from a designated folder path. These images are converted into numpy arrays and stored in a list. Optionally, visualization of the collected images can be performed. Subsequently, the list of image arrays is consolidated into a numpy array, which organizes the data into a suitable format for model training. Following this, the arrays undergo transposition to align with the expected input structure of the machine learning model. Labels are then assigned to the datasets, representing the target classes for the corresponding input data. Finally, TensorFlow 'Dataset' objects are created from the input features and labels, facilitating the construction of training, validation, and testing data loaders. This comprehensive data preprocessing framework sets the stage for subsequent model development and evaluation in the realm of medical imaging analysis. The pre-processed data is then divided into three parts mainly for the training, testing and validation.

Model Building:

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) have emerged as powerful tools for image analysis tasks, owing to their ability to automatically learn hierarchical representations from raw pixel data. Initially developed for 2D images, CNNs have been widely applied in tasks such as image classification, object detection, and segmentation, revolutionizing various fields including computer vision and medical imaging.

In the context of medical imaging analysis, the inherent complexity of volumetric data poses unique challenges. Unlike conventional 2D images, medical scans such as MRIs, CTs, and PET scans are volumetric in nature, comprising a stack of 2D slices representing different anatomical or functional aspects. The volumetric nature of these datasets introduces rich spatial dependencies across three dimensions, necessitating specialized architectures capable of effectively capturing and leveraging this spatial information.

This is where 3D CNNs come into play. Unlike their 2D counterparts, 3D CNNs are specifically designed to operate on volumetric data, allowing them to process information across three spatial dimensions. By extending the convolutional operation into the third dimension, 3D CNNs can capture spatial features and patterns that are crucial for accurate diagnosis and treatment planning in medical imaging applications.

The adaptation of CNNs to 3D data is particularly advantageous in medical imaging, where accurate spatial representation is essential for tasks such as lesion detection, organ segmentation, and disease classification. Traditional 2D CNNs may not fully exploit the spatial information inherent in volumetric medical images, potentially leading to suboptimal performance in these critical tasks.

By leveraging 3D CNNs, researchers and healthcare professionals can harness the full richness of volumetric medical data. These architectures are adept at capturing spatial dependencies across three dimensions, facilitating more accurate and comprehensive analysis of medical images. The adoption of 3D CNNs holds immense potential to revolutionize medical imaging analysis, leading to improved diagnostic accuracy, enhanced treatment planning, and ultimately, better patient outcomes.

The architecture design considerations encompass a meticulous selection and integration of components tailored to exploit the unique characteristics of medical imaging data:

Convolutional Layers: The heart of the 3D CNN architecture lies in its convolutional layers. Unlike traditional 2D CNNs, which operate on two-dimensional images, 3D CNNs leverage filters that slide across three dimensions to capture volumetric patterns in medical images. This enables the model to effectively extract spatial features, crucial for tasks such as lesion detection, organ segmentation, and disease classification.

Pooling Layers: Max pooling layers play a pivotal role in down-sampling spatial dimensions while retaining essential features. By reducing the spatial resolution of feature maps, these layers mitigate computational complexity and prevent overfitting. Moreover, they help preserve important spatial information, facilitating robust feature extraction from volumetric data.

Batch Normalization: Batch normalization is instrumental in stabilizing and accelerating the training process by normalizing activations within each mini-batch during training. This technique ensures that the model learns more efficiently by reducing internal covariate shift, thereby enhancing convergence and generalization.

Global Pooling: Global average pooling serves as a dimensionality reduction technique, aggregating feature maps across all spatial dimensions to generate fixed-length feature

vectors. By summarizing spatial information in this manner, global pooling enables the model to focus on the most discriminative features while reducing computational complexity.

Dense Layers: Dense layers are responsible for learning complex, non-linear mappings from the extracted features to the output classes. By introducing fully connected layers, the model can capture high-level representations of the input data, facilitating higher-level decision-making in medical image analysis tasks.

Dropout Regularization: Dropout regularization is incorporated into the architecture to mitigate overfitting and improve generalization capabilities. By randomly deactivating neurons during training, dropout prevents the model from relying too heavily on individual units, encouraging robust feature learning and enhancing model performance on unseen data.

In the proposed 3D CNN architecture for medical imaging analysis, careful consideration is given to the design of the output layer and the choice of activation function. This section discusses the rationale behind these decisions and their implications for model performance. The output layer of the 3D CNN is pivotal in generating predictions or classifications based on the extracted features from the preceding layers. In our architecture, the output layer employs a sigmoid activation function. Unlike traditional activation functions such as softmax, which are typically used for single-label classification tasks, the sigmoid activation function is well-suited for multi-label classification scenarios prevalent in medical imaging analysis. By employing the sigmoid activation function, our model is capable of producing independent probabilities for each class or label, allowing for the simultaneous prediction of multiple diagnostic categories within a single input image. This flexibility is particularly advantageous in medical imaging, where a single image may contain manifestations of multiple conditions or abnormalities requiring simultaneous assessment. Moreover, the dimensionality of the output layer aligns with the number of target classes or labels present in the medical imaging dataset. This ensures that the model's predictions are appropriately scaled to match the granularity of diagnostic categories encoded within the dataset, facilitating accurate classification and interpretation of medical images.

Fig 2: Model Architecture

3D-CNN

Layer	Output Shape	Param
Input_1	[(None, 64, 64, 8, 1)]	0
conv3d	(None, 64, 64, 8, 8)	224
max_pooling3d	(None, 32, 32, 4, 8)	0
batch_normalization	(None, 32, 32, 4, 8)	32
conv3d_1	(None, 32, 32, 4, 8)	1736
max_pooling3d_1	(None, 16, 16, 2, 8)	0
batch_normalization_1	(None, 16, 16, 2, 8)	32
conv3d_2	(None, 16, 16, 2, 16)	3472
max_pooling3d_2	(None, 8, 8, 1, 16)	0
batch_normalization_2	(None, 8, 8, 1, 16)	64
conv3d_3	(None, 8, 8, 1, 32)	13856
max_pooling3d_3	(None, 4, 4, 1, 32)	0
batch_normalization_3	(None, 4, 4, 1, 32)	128
global_average_pooling3d	(None, 32)	0
dense	(None, 512)	16896
dropout	(None, 512)	0
dense_1	(None, 4)	2052

Total params	38,492
Trainable params	38,364

Training Strategy:

The training strategy employed in the provided code segment involves several key components aimed at optimizing the performance of the 3D convolutional neural network (CNN) model for medical image classification. Firstly, the Adam optimizer is utilized with a learning rate of 0.001, alongside configurable parameters including beta_1, beta_2, epsilon, and decay, enabling efficient gradient-based optimization during training. This optimizer is well-suited for non-convex optimization problems like neural network training, offering adaptive learning rates and momentum adjustments.

The model is compiled using the categorical cross-entropy loss function, which is commonly employed for multi-class classification tasks. This loss function quantifies the disparity between the predicted probability distributions and the true class labels, guiding the model towards minimizing classification errors during training. Additionally, the accuracy metric is specified to monitor the classification performance of the model on both the training and validation datasets, providing insights into its efficacy in correctly categorizing medical images.

To facilitate model checkpointing and ensure the preservation of the best-performing model weights, a ModelCheckpoint callback is employed. This callback monitors the validation accuracy metric and saves the model weights to a designated file only when an improvement in validation accuracy is observed. By enabling the save_best_only parameter, the callback ensures that only the model with the highest validation accuracy is retained, preventing overfitting to the training data.

Furthermore, a ReduceLROnPlateau callback is utilized to dynamically adjust the learning rate during training based on the observed behavior of the validation loss. This callback reduces the learning rate by a factor of 0.5 if no improvement in validation loss is detected for a specified number of epochs (patience), thereby facilitating finer convergence towards the optimal model parameters and potentially overcoming local minima in the optimization landscape.

Overall, this training strategy integrates adaptive optimization techniques, effective loss monitoring, and dynamic learning rate adjustment mechanisms, aimed at maximizing the classification performance of the 3D CNN model on medical image datasets while mitigating the risk of overfitting and ensuring convergence towards an optimal solution.

RESULTS

In this study, we employed both machine learning and deep learning techniques to analyse and classify medical imaging data. For the machine learning approach, we utilized five distinct models: Random Forests, K-Nearest Neighbours (KNN), Logistic Regression, Support Vector Machine (SVM), and Decision Tree. These models yielded varying levels of accuracy, with Random Forests achieving 75%, KNN 60%, Logistic Regression 79%, SVM 78%, and Decision Tree 65%. Despite the reasonably good performance of some of these models, they were outperformed by our deep learning approach.

Our deep learning model, a 3D Convolutional Neural Network (3D CNN), demonstrated superior performance metrics after being trained for 150 epochs. The confusion matrix for the 3D CNN is as follows:

Fig 3: Confusion Matrix

The 3D CNN achieved an accuracy of 91.57%, precision of 92.08%, recall of 91.57%, and an F1 score of 91.39%. These results highlight the model’s robustness and ability to accurately classify medical images across multiple categories. Specifically, the true positives (TP) for each class were [22, 21, 17, 16], false positives (FP) were [3, 2, 2, 0], false negatives (FN) were [0, 0, 3, 4], and true negatives (TN) were [58, 60, 61, 63]. The mean sensitivity (recall) of the model was calculated to be 91.25%, and the mean specificity was 97.17%, indicating a high level of performance in distinguishing between different classes.

During the training phase, continuous monitoring of both accuracy and loss metrics was conducted to ensure optimal model performance. This monitoring was visually represented through two graphs, illustrating the trends and progress of these metrics over the course of training.

Fig 4: Monitoring Accuracy

Fig 5: Monitoring Loss

Additionally, a Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve was utilized to evaluate the model’s performance across all four classes, providing further insights into its classification capabilities.

Fig 6: ROC Curve

In conclusion, the combination of machine learning and deep learning techniques provided a comprehensive analysis framework, with the 3D CNN demonstrating significant advantages in accuracy and overall performance for medical image classification. The detailed metrics and continuous monitoring strategies underscore the effectiveness and reliability of the proposed deep learning model in clinical applications.

Conclusion

In conclusion, our project, deteCT, presents a robust solution for detecting deepfake CT scans, combining advanced technological innovation with practical usability. The core of our approach lies in the development of a 3D convolutional neural network (3D CNN) model specifically designed to analyze the three-dimensional structures of CT scans. This model was meticulously trained on a diverse dataset, encompassing a wide range of scenarios and variations, to ensure its reliability and effectiveness in real-world applications. The rigorous training process led to impressive performance metrics, showcasing the model's high accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score. The confusion matrix and ROC curve analyses further validated the model's capability to distinguish between authentic and manipulated CT images with minimal error rates. This advanced detection mechanism is crucial for maintaining the integrity of medical diagnoses and ensuring patient safety. By integrating this powerful model into a user-friendly interface built with Streamlit, we have made sophisticated deepfake detection accessible to medical professionals, enabling them to upload and verify CT scans effortlessly. Overall, deteCT exemplifies how cutting-edge machine learning techniques can be applied to critical healthcare challenges, providing a reliable and efficient tool for enhancing the trustworthiness of medical-imaging.

Future Challenges

Despite the promising results of our 3D CNN model in medical image classification, several future challenges must be addressed to advance this research. First, the generalizability of the model across diverse medical imaging modalities and different patient demographics remains a critical issue. Medical imaging datasets often vary significantly in terms of image quality, resolution, and patient population, necessitating extensive validation across multiple datasets to ensure robust performance. Additionally, the limited availability of annotated medical imaging data poses a significant challenge. High-quality annotations are typically obtained through expert radiologists, making the annotation process time-consuming and costly. Leveraging semi-supervised learning or transfer learning techniques could mitigate this issue by maximizing the utility of available labeled data.

Another challenge lies in the interpretability of deep learning models. Clinicians require transparent and explainable models to trust and adopt AI-driven diagnostics in clinical settings. Developing methods to interpret and visualize the decision-making process of 3D CNNs will be crucial in fostering clinical acceptance. Moreover, computational efficiency is a concern, as 3D CNNs are resource-intensive, demanding substantial computational power for both training

and inference. Optimizing these models for real-time applications and deploying them on standard medical imaging hardware will be essential for practical implementation.

Regulatory and ethical considerations also present challenges. Ensuring compliance with healthcare regulations, safeguarding patient privacy, and addressing biases within AI models are paramount. Ethical issues related to AI decision-making, such as accountability and transparency, must be rigorously addressed to align with clinical standards and societal expectations.

Lastly, continuous model updates and maintenance are necessary to adapt to evolving medical standards and new data, requiring a dynamic and sustainable framework for long-term integration into healthcare systems. Addressing these challenges will be pivotal in realizing the full potential of 3D CNNs in medical imaging and ensuring their safe and effective deployment in clinical practice.

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